

TASK ALLOCATION AND EMPLOYEE PRODUCTIVITY OF CHEMICAL MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA

¹Sunday, Ikechukwu Emmanuel, ²Ugochukwu, Loveth Ngozi Ph.D. and ³Nwatu, Emmanuel Chukwuemeka Ph.D.

¹Business School, Department of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu State.

²Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Management Sciences, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu State.

³Department of Business Management, Faculty of Management Sciences, University of Calabar, Calabar, Cross Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract: The study evaluated Task allocation and employee productivity of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to: Examine the relationship between job analysis and employee output and Evaluate the relationship between skill matching and employee retention of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The study was based on the three (3) selected Chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis with high number of staff and long years of establishment. The total population for the study was two hundred and seventy three (273). The study made use of the whole due to its small number. A survey design was adopted for the study. Instrument used for data collection was the questionnaire and interviews. Two hundred and fifty one (251) copies of questionnaire were properly completed and returned. The findings indicated that Job analysis had significant positive relationship with employee output, $Z(10.541, P. < .05)$ and Skill matching had significant positive relationship with employee retention of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State, $Z(11.062, P. < .05)$. The study concluded that Job analysis and Skill matching had significant positive relationship with employee output and employee retention of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The study recommended among others that to enhance employee output in chemical manufacturing firms, it is crucial to implement a structured and continuous job analysis process.

Keywords: Employee output, skill matching, employee productivity, Employee retention, job analysis, task allocation

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

Team productivity is critical for any organization seeking to expand. Moreover, if productivity declines, organizations risk losing business and clients, leading to enormous setbacks. Task management directly affects productivity, business growth, and management. Hence, managers must understand what task management is and how it affects effectiveness and productivity at work (Petrov, 2025). Effective task allocation is crucial for boosting employee productivity by ensuring tasks are assigned to individuals with the right skills and experience, leading to higher output and job satisfaction. Resource allocation plays a vital role in project management, enabling organizations, particularly professional services organizations, to effectively plan, manage, and utilize their resources. However, many professional services organizations face challenges when it comes to resource allocation, which can significantly impact project success, client satisfaction, and overall productivity (Zhied, 2024).

Increasing productivity in an organization involves improving employee performance, streamlining operations, and leveraging technology to deliver better services and achieve financial goals. Krithika, (2022) asserts that employee productivity is critical to the success of companies; more and more productive the employees are, the greater ideas they will create. Acknowledging employee productivity as a system impacting all employees is a wonderful place to start. Employee productivity is an essential part of the success of an organization. Because employees are the backbone of your business, it makes complete sense to invest time and money in numerous components that help boost employee productivity (Krithika, 2022). For any organization to grow and be a success, it's crucial that employees are productive as employee productivity improvement can have a positive impact on the workplace experience of all employees.

Productivity in an organization is influenced by various factors, including employee training, work-life balance, extrinsic rewards and technological advancements. McKinsey, (2025) opined that improving productivity is akin to climbing a mountain whose slope sharply steepens as one scales. The initial stages are gentle slopes, and classic cost-reduction approaches—such as optimizing the procurement process, managing travel and entertainment costs, and cutting spending on certain projects—can deliver results. But above a certain altitude, the challenges become more complex. Employee productivity is a crucial factor in the success of every organization. By focusing on factors that drive employee motivation, training, and engagement, firms can significantly improve their overall performance and profitability. Hence the need for the study on task allocation and employee productivity of chemical manufacturing firms.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Effective task allocation helps in managing time more efficiently. underutilization of resources, over allocation leading to burnout or delays, and mismatches between tasks and individual skills or capabilities affects the performance and productivity of every organization. By understanding the workloads of team members, managers can avoid overloading individuals and ensure that deadlines

are met without compromising quality. For any organization to grow and be a success, it's crucial that employees are productive.

Improvement of productivity is a central issue in present-day organizations. Task allocation challenges arises in an organization according to the tasks involved these organizations. Chemical manufacturing firms faces challenges due to dynamic production demands, evolving regulatory landscapes, and the need for efficient and accurate chemical handling. Furthermore, these problems often arise as a result of poor job analysis and unaligned skill matching in the organization.

Understanding the employee's attitude in today's dynamic work environment poses a challenge for organisations. The chemical industry typically deals with a large number of raw materials and finished goods, and the movement of these materials can be complex and difficult to track. However, these constraints can be overcome through identification and sourcing for its solution as neglect to them can result to reduced employee output and employee retention. Hence, to solve these constraints, the study aimed to evaluate task allocation and employee productivity of Chemical manufacturing firms.

1.3 Objectives of the study

The specific objective of the study was to evaluate Task allocation and employee productivity of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to;

- i. Examine the relationship between job analysis and employee output of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State.
- ii. Evaluate the relationship between skill matching and employee retention of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- i. What is the relationship between job analysis and employee output of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State.
- ii. What is the skill matching and employee retention of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

1.5 Statement of hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study

- i. Job analysis has relationship with employee output of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State.
- ii. Skill matching has relationship with employee retention of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

1.6 Scope of the study

The study was on task allocation and employee productivity of chemical manufacturing firms. The key variables of the study were job analysis and skill matching (independent variable) and Employee output and employee retention (dependent variable)

2.0 Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual review

2.1.1 Task allocation

Task Allocation is a fundamental aspect of an organisation, a productivity tool designed to enhance team collaboration and efficiency. Task Allocation is a strategic process in project management where tasks are distributed among team members or resources to efficiently achieve project goals. This process involves assessing the skills, strengths, and workloads of team members to ensure that tasks are assigned to the most suitable individuals (LiftOs, 2024). It plays a crucial role in achieving goals, meeting deadlines, and maximizing productivity. Task allocation, also known as work allocation or workload distribution, refers to the strategic assignment of tasks and responsibilities within a project or organization to ensure efficient resource utilization and optimal performance. It plays a crucial role in achieving goals, meeting deadlines, and maximizing productivity (Prohance, 2025). Tasks are allocated in a way that the workload is distributed equally so that some employees do not feel overburdened with the work at hand while others are not left with too little work to do. By allocating tasks, you can ensure that resources such as time, skills and tools are used optimally. This approach maximises the utilization of resources and minimizes waste (Kashyap, 2025).

2.1.2 Components of task allocation used in the study

2.1.2.1 Job analysis

Job analysis can be defined as a methodical procedure of gathering, documenting, and analyzing relevant information about a particular job role (Myjobmag, 2025). Job analysis involves systematically gathering information about the tasks, duties, responsibilities, and required skills of specific job roles within an organization. It involves examining various aspects of the job, including duties, tasks, skills, and the work environment, to create a clear picture of what the job entails. Job analysis plays a pivotal role in organizational management and human resources. (Myjobmag, 2025). In the banking sector, job satisfaction is often linked to employee compensation. Employees who are satisfied with their salaries, benefits, and job security are more likely to be motivated and committed to their work.

2.1.2.2 Skill matching

Skills Matching represents the degree of successful utilisation of skills, the extent to which skills are effectively matched in the labour market. Skill matching refers to connecting individuals based on the skills they seek and offer. The foundation of matching templates, advanced matching algorithm is designed to pair individuals within organisations at scale, while maintaining high accuracy. This

element of matching automation helps streamline organisation's operations, significantly reducing the time spent on manual pairings (Pursell, 2024). Matching is an essential skill, helping to improve a number of cognitive abilities like visual memory, short term memory and pattern recognition. Matching also helps with focus: it's no accident that the classic game of memory, played with pairs of cards arranged face-down, is sometimes called "concentration." Efficient job description and successful skill matching require standard terminologies for jobs and their requirements/qualifications, such as the 'European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations' (ESCO) (Stalidis and Kyriazidou, 2023)

2.1.3 Employee productivity

Employee productivity, sometimes referred to as workforce productivity, is an assessment of the efficiency of a worker or group of workers. Productivity may be evaluated in terms of the output of an employee over a specific time. Typically, the productivity of a given worker is assessed relative to an average for employees doing similar work (Kirvan, 2025). The productivity of employees reflects the efficiency level indicating the time taken to perform a particular task. When the employees tend to be productive, they perform a particular task more efficiently and effectively within a given time frame (Singh and Chaudhary, 2022). Success of any organization relies upon the productivity of its workforce, employee productivity is an important consideration for businesses. Loss of employee productivity can have different consequences, such as the inability to ship the required numbers of components to customers or failure to deliver government-mandated reports on time

2.1.4 Components of employee productivity used in the study

2.1.4.1 Employee Output

Employee output refers to the value generated by an individual or group of employees, which will differ depending upon the nature of the job role and organisation. In some roles, it's easy to identify the value the employee generates (Fletcher, 2024). Employee performance refers to how well employees fulfill their responsibilities, meet goals, and contribute to organizational objectives. Employee output can be measured as the amount of work an employee can get done within a certain period of time. The most obvious benefit of high employee productivity is that more work is being done within your business. That might mean more products are being manufactured, more services delivered, more customers helped, and so on. The most obvious benefit of high employee productivity is that more work is being done within your business. That might mean more products are being manufactured, more services delivered and more customers helped (Qualtrics, 2025).

2.1.4.2 Employee Retention

Employee retention refers to an organisation's ability to keep its employees, reduce turnover and minimize the number of employees who leave the company, either voluntarily or involuntarily. Gillis, Baker and Shaun, (2025) defined employee retention as the organizational goal of keeping productive and talented workers and reducing turnover by fostering a positive work atmosphere to promote

engagement. This includes showing appreciation to employees, providing competitive pay and benefits, and encouraging a healthy work-life balance. Managing for employee retention involves strategic actions to keep employees motivated and focused so they elect to remain employed and fully productive for the benefit of the organization (Toolkit, 2024). A comprehensive employee retention program can play a vital role in both attracting and retaining key employees, as well as in reducing turnover and its related costs. All of these contribute to an organization's productivity and overall business performance. It is more efficient to retain a quality employee than to recruit, train and orient a replacement employee of the same quality.

2.2 Theoretical Review

Goal setting theory

The Goal Setting Theory was primarily proposed by Edwin Locke and Gary Latham. They worked together to develop and refine the theory, which emphasizes the link between goal setting and task performance. Locke initially introduced the core concept in his 1968 paper, "Toward a Theory of Task Motivation and Incentives". Latham later collaborated with Locke to further expand and refine the theory. Goal setting theory asserts that specific, challenging goals lead to higher performance than vague goals or no goals at all. It also posits that the higher the goal, the higher the individual's performance, and that factors like feedback or participation are only effective if they contribute to the setting of specific, challenging goals. Essentially, the theory emphasizes the importance of clear, difficult goals for motivating and enhancing individual performance.

This theory posits that setting specific, challenging, and achievable goals leads to higher levels of employee productivity. When employees are given clear targets, they are more motivated to work harder to meet them. However, it's important to note that goals alone are not sufficient; commitment, teamwork, and support are also necessary. Individuals are more likely to exert greater effort and achieve better results when they are striving to meet more difficult and ambitious goals.

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 The relationship between job analysis and employee output of chemical manufacturing firms

Singh and Chaudhary, (2022) Employee Productivity: An Analysis of Dimensions and Methodology through Systematic Literature Review. The main purpose of this comprehensive review of literature is to find out the determinants measuring employee productivity and to address the research gap for further studies. This research paper emphasises undertaking a systematic review of literature on employee productivity, to understand its concept, methodology used and to identify different industries in which the studies have been conducted so far. For this purpose, 114 research papers pertaining to employee productivity have been downloaded, of which 77 relevant articles were identified and reviewed for measuring employee productivity and its determinants. This study identified various determinants measuring employee productivity comprehending motivation, work-

life balance work environment, training, stress, workplace health, compensation, performance appraisal, and job satisfaction. Further, it is revealed that there were only a few studies conducted on employee productivity in India.

Stalidis and Kyriazidou, (2023) Job Role Description and Skill Matching in a Rapidly Changing Labor Market Using Knowledge Engineering. The aim of this paper is to search whether ESCO—as the most representative job-related information model—has been adopted in the current rapidly evolving job market and the degree in which standardized job roles and their related skillsets are in line with the content found in the current job ads. Additionally, we intend to identify possible missing elements of this framework, towards its wider adoption and advanced skill-matching recommendation systems. As a representative case, the study was focused on selected IT professions in the Greek labor market. To this end, we applied a text mining process to 400 job ads, in order to capture the skillsets required by recruiting companies. The identified requirements for the selected job roles were used to model part of the Greek IT labor market. This model was then compared with the suggested requirements of the ESCO framework. It was found that the degree of matching between the skills in ads and the skills suggested by ESCO, is notably small and that the skills frequently requested in current IT job ads that were not included in ESCO, were mostly related to recently developed technologies and to soft skills

Udealor, Okereke and Oshi (2023). Examined value creation innovation and productivity of deposit money banks in Rives State, Nigeria”. This study examined the relationship between value creation innovation and productivity of deposit money banks in rives state. The cross-sectional survey was employed and a population two hundred and four (204) of 17 Deposit Money Banks were covered. The sample size was determined using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table. Copies of questionnaire were administered to respondents. The simple random sampling technique was employed and data was analyzed using Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficient. The findings revealed a significant relationship between the dimensions of value creation Innovation (leadership capabilities and new technology/equipment) and productivity. It was concluded that organization that indulge in value creation innovation in terms leadership capabilities and new technology/equipment tends to yield an increase in the service quality in a due time and overall productivity. The study recommended amongst others that Management of Deposit money banks should engage in value creation innovation that will inform their decisions and actions towards enhancing better performance and productivity.

Egrinya and Omang (2024) conducted a study on behavior modification: A Panacea for Increasing Productivity in Deposit-Money Bank in South-South, Nigeria. The study sought to determine the imperativeness of behaviour modification as a panacea for increasing productivity in the deposit-money bank in South-south, Nigeria. The concept behaviour modification is an accepted concept to inculcate in an employee the ethical behaviour that will ensure the attainment of organisation objectives. The specific objectives were (i) Ascertain the extent to which training, retraining and reward for hard work enhances productivity in the deposit-money bank in South-south, Nigeria. (ii)

To a large extent reinforcement techniques has significant effect on workers lukewarm attitudes to work in the deposit-money bank in South-south, Nigeria. (iii) To a large extent learning techniques enhances desirable and ethical behaviour of workers in the deposit-money bank in South-south, Nigeria. The study adopted the survey design. The population of the study consisted of 578 respondents drawn from 344 various deposit-money banks operational in South-south, Nigeria. A sample size of 231 was drawn from the population using Krejcie and Morgan, (1970), sample size determination. Primary data was used for the study and collected through the use of structured five-point likert scale questionnaire and interview method. The hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation, (PPMC) technique for hypotheses one and two. Meanwhile, Simple Linear regression was used for hypothesis three. The findings revealed that: Training, retraining and reward for hard working enhances productivity in the deposit-money bank, in South-south, Nigeria ($r = .846$, $p < 0.05$). To a large extent Reinforcement techniques has significant positive effects on workers lukewarm attitudes to work, in the deposit-money bank, in South-south, Nigeria ($r = .754$, $p < 0.05$). To a large extent Learning techniques enhances desirable and ethical behaviours of workers in the deposit-money bank, in South-south, Nigeria ($r = .745$, $p < 0.05$). Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that management staff should adopt the various behaviour modification techniques that is appropriate in changing behaviours to desirable and ethical attitudes that would ensure the effectiveness and efficiency of the workers and the attainment of the Organisational objective.

Odunayo, (2024) Impact of Performance Evaluation on Employees' Productivity in Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State, Nigeria. This study sought to determine the effect of performance evaluation on employee productivity in deposit money banks in Lagos State. The study adopts survey research design. The population of this study consist of 192 employees of two selected Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State. The study adopted total enumeration method in determining the sample size. The study collected primary data with the help of questionnaire. Data was collected from respondents using a structured questionnaire. Ordinary least square regression model was used to assess the nature and degree of relationship between dependent variable and independent variables. Findings from the study indicated that the use of performance appraisal has significant effect on employee productivity. Specifically, findings revealed that managerial review and peer review have significant effect and enhanced employee productivity.

The study of Nduka, Maduka and Nnawuchi, (2025) Employee placement and performance of deposit money banks in Enugu State. The study examined the Employee placement and performance of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to: examine the relationship between job analysis and operational efficiency; and evaluate the relationship between skill assessment and operational cost reduction of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria. A survey design was adopted for the study. The study was based on the four (4) selected banks with

international recognitions out of seven (7) of them in Nigeria and within Enugu metropolis with high number of staff and long years of establishment namely: Guaranty trust Bank, First bank Plc, United bank of Africa and Zenith bank. The total population for the study was two hundred and sixty three (263). The study made use of the whole due to its small number. Instrument used for data collection was the questionnaire. Two hundred and forty five (245) copies of questionnaire were properly completed and returned. That gave 93 percent response rate. Data was presented and analyzed with mean score and standard deviations and Z – test was used to test the hypotheses with aid of Special Package for Statistical Software (SPSS). The findings indicated that Job analysis had significant positive relationship with operational efficiency, Nigeria. $Z = 9.823$, $P. = 0.05$ and Skill assessment had significant positive relationship with operational cost reduction of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria. $Z = 11.500$, $P. = 0.05$. The study concluded that Job analysis and Skill assessment had significant positive relationship with operational efficiency and operational cost reduction of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study recommended among others that Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State should conduct regular and detailed job analyses to clearly define role expectations, responsibilities, and required qualifications, ensuring proper alignment during employee placement.

2.3.2 Skill matching and employee retention of chemical manufacturing firms

Nosike and Okerekeoti, (2022) Productivity and Organizational Performance: Evidence from Pharmaceutical Firms in Nigeria of the Creative Commons Attribution License. This study examined the relationship between employee productivity and organizational performance of pharmaceutical firms in Ebonyi State, Nigeria. Survey research design was adopted, and data were gathered through the questionnaires administered to respondents. Pearson coefficient correlation was employed to test the hypotheses via SPSS version 20.0. From the analysis, the study concluded that employee motivation and organizational climate have positive significant relationship with organizational performance of pharmaceutical firms in Ebonyi State, Nigeria. Based on the results, this study recommended among others that Businesses should guarantee that feedback is provided on a regular basis so that appraisers can determine whether they are fulfilling management expectations or the organization's goals. To empower employees, there should be rewards for excellent accomplishments as well as training for unfavorable results.

Yousra, Asim, Omer and Ayesha, (2024) examined the Impact of HRM Practices on Employee Retention: Moderating Role of Job Satisfaction. This study aims to explore the impact of compensation, training, and development (T&D), and working conditions on employee retention within the manufacturing sector of Pakistan, with a specific focus on the mediating role of job satisfaction. Employing a convenience sampling strategy, the research collected data from 382 employees across various manufacturing firms in Pakistan. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was conducted using Smart PLS software to analyze the data and test the proposed hypotheses. The

findings of the study reveal that compensation, training and development, and working conditions have a direct and positive impact on employee retention. Moreover, the results highlight the significant mediating role of job satisfaction in the relationship between these organizational factors and employee retention. All direct and indirect hypotheses proposed in the study were accepted, confirming the mediating influence of job satisfaction and underscoring its critical role in

Odoh, (2024) conducted a study on Time Management and Employee Productivity in Government Institutions in Delta State. The value of time management lies in the fact that people have too many tasks they need to do but not enough time for the things that they want to do. The study therefore, examined time management and employee productivity in government institutions in Delta State. The study adopted Time Management Quadrant theory. The study utilized secondary source of data. The study revealed that effective time management not only affects the productivity of employees, but also helps to cope with stress, conflicts and pressure more efficiently. It also helps them maintain a healthy work-life balance and keeps them motivated. The recommended that time should be set for the accomplishment of all activities by government at all levels including the core ministries. Adequate provisions should be made for the attainment of the goals set, among others

Jooss, Collings, McMackin and Dickmann (2024) A skill-matching perspective on talent mismanagement: developing strategic agility. Despite two decades of evolution as an area of research and practice, talent management faces ongoing criticism for being overly static in its approach, offering little in terms of enabling strategic agility. This is problematic as organizations increasingly rely on strategic agility to manage their dynamic business operations. Drawing on matching theory and adopting an agility lens, we explore the link between talent management and strategic agility. Through a qualitative research design, encompassing 34 interviews in 15 organizations, we explicate a skills-matching perspective on talent management, including initial and dynamic skills-matching in external and internal labor markets. Through this process, organizations can build a set of dynamic capabilities, underlying two meta-capabilities, strategic sensitivity and resource fluidity, which enable strategic agility. In doing so, we portray skills-matching as an illustration of a processual view on talent management and create a model of developing strategic agility through skills-matching, responsive to external and internal demands

2.4 Gap in Empirical Review

The study on task allocation and employee productivity of chemical manufacturing firms reviewed empirical literatures which were of great value to the study. These literatures include the study of Udealor, Okereke and Oshi, (2023). Examined value creation innovation and productivity of deposit money banks in Rives State, Nigeria”. Stalidis and Kyriazidou, (2023) Job Role Description and Skill Matching in a Rapidly Changing Labor Market Using Knowledge Engineering. Egrinya and Omang (2024) conducted a study on behavior modification: A Panacea for Increasing Productivity in Deposit-Money Bank in South-South, Nigeria and Singh and Chaudhary, (2022) Employee Productivity: An

Analysis of Dimensions and Methodology through Systematic Literature Review e.t.c. The researcher observed that these studies were conducted in South East Nigeria and were also current studies which made them relevant for the present study. However, most of these studies were examined in respect of deposit money banks with few/non in chemical manufacturing firms. The findings showed that task allocation are of great impact in the productivity of deposit money banks. Hence, the motivation of the researcher to examine task allocation and employee productivity of chemical manufacturing firms.

3.0 Methodology

The study was based on the three (3) selected Chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis with high number of staff and long years of establishment. The total population for the study was two hundred and seventy three (273). The study made use of the whole due to its small number. A survey design was adopted for the study. Instrument used for data collection was the questionnaire and interviews. Two hundred and fifty one (251) copies of questionnaire were properly completed and returned. That gave 92 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.84 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score (3.0 and above agreed while below 3.0 disagreed) and Z – test was used to test the hypotheses with aid of Special Package for Statistical Software (SPSS).

4.0 Data Presentation and Analyses

4.1 Data Presentation

Table 4.1.1: Responses on the relationship between job analysis and employee output of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	Decision
1	Well-trained and skilled employees can perform tasks more efficiently, reducing operational costs.	480 96 38.2	188 47 18.7	195 65 25.9	18 9 3.6	34 34 13.5	915 251 100.0	3.65	1.373	Agree
2	Focusing on retaining and developing existing skilled staff can lead to cost savings by reducing the need for new hires	835 167 66.5	188 47 18.7	39 13 5.2	10 5 2.0	19 19 7.6	1091 251 100.0	4.35	1.168	Agree
3	Precise job requirements help attract suitable candidates, reducing the need for extensive training and potentially avoiding costly mismatches	620 124 49.4	188 47 18.7	159 53 21.1	10 5 2.0	22 22 8.8	999 251 100.0	3.98	1.257	Agree

4	Hiring skilled employees initially reduces the need for extensive training, saving on training expenses.	565	324	39	8	40	976					Agree
		113	81	13	4	40	251					
		45.0	32.3	5.2	1.6	15.9	100.0	3.89	1.413			
5	Attracting and retaining talent reduces the costs associated with frequent recruitment, training, and the loss of productivity from employee turnover.	730	220	15	4	43	1012					Agree
		146	55	5	2	43	251					
		58.2	21.9	2.0	.8	17.1	100.0	4.03	1.477			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.98	1.337	6		

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.1.1, 143 respondents out of 251 representing 56.9 percent agreed that Well-trained and skilled employees can perform tasks more efficiently, reducing operational costs with the mean score of 3.65 and standard deviation of 1.373. 214 respondents representing 85.2 percent agreed that focusing on retaining and developing existing skilled staff can lead to cost savings by reducing the need for new hires with mean score of 4.35 and standard deviation of 1.168. 171 respondents representing 68.1 percent agreed that when precise job requirements help attract suitable candidates, reducing the need for extensive training and potentially avoiding costly mismatches with mean score of 3.98 and standard deviation of 1.257. 194 respondents representing 77.3 percent agreed that with Hiring skilled employees initially reduces the need for extensive training, saving on training expenses with mean score of 3.89 and standard deviation of 1.413. 201 respondents representing 80.1 percent agreed that Attracting and retaining talent reduces the costs associated with frequent recruitment, training, and the loss of productivity from employee turnover with a mean score of 4.05 and standard deviation 1.477

Table 4.1.2: Responses on the relationship between skill matching and employee retention of chemical manufacturing firms

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Training helps employees acquire new skills and update their knowledge, making them more competent in their roles	455	356	15	46	43	915			Agree
		91	89	5	23	43	251			
		36.3	35.5	2.0	9.2	17.1	100.0	3.65	1.474	
2	A trained workforce is better equipped to handle customer inquiries and provide excellent service, potentially leading to increased customer	510	544	15	2	7	1078			Agree
		102	136	5	1	7	251			
		40.6	54.2	2.0	.4	2.8	100.0	4.29	.780	

retention and satisfaction.

3	Increased revenue and reduced costs can lead to higher profits, allowing the bank to reinvest in further training and development.	485	528	21	20	5	1059			Agree	
		97	132	7	10	5	251				
		38.6	52.6	2.8	4.0	2.0	100.0	4.22	.841		
4	A well-trained workforce is generally more productive, leading to greater output and reduced need for overtime or hiring additional staff.	280	612	21	60	5	978			Agree	
		56	153	7	30	5	251				
		22.3	61.0	2.8	12.0	2.0	100.0	3.90	.949		
5	Proper training can minimize errors, rework, and waste, further contributing to efficiency and cost reduction.	430	288	36	12	50	816			Agree	
		86	97	12	6	50	251				
		34.3	38.6	4.8	2.4	19.9	100.0	3.65	1.471		
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								4.02	1.111	8	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.1.2, 180 respondents out of 251 representing 71.8 percent agreed that Training helps employees acquire new skills and update their knowledge, making them more competent in their roles with the mean score of 3.65 and standard deviation of 1.474. 238 respondents representing 94.8 percent agreed that a trained workforce is better equipped to handle customer inquiries and provide excellent service, potentially leading to increased customer retention and satisfaction with mean score of 4.29 and standard deviation of .780. 229 respondents representing 91.2 percent agreed that increased revenue and reduced costs can lead to higher profits, allowing the bank to reinvest in further training and development with mean score of 4.22 and standard deviation of .841. 209 respondents representing 83.3 percent agreed that with a well-trained workforce is generally more productive, leading to greater output and reduced need for overtime or hiring additional staff with mean score of 3.90 and standard deviation of .949. 183 respondents representing 72.9 percent agreed that Proper training can minimize errors, rework, and waste, further contributing to efficiency and cost reduction with a mean score of 3.65 and standard deviation 1.471

4.2 Test on Hypotheses

4.2.1 Hypotheses One: Job analysis has significant relationship with employee output of chemical manufacturing firms

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	Well-trained and skilled employees can perform tasks more efficiently, reducing operational costs.	Focusing on retaining and developing existing skilled staff can lead to cost savings by reducing the need for new hires	Precise job requirements help attract suitable candidates, reducing the need for extensive training and potentially avoiding costly mismatches	Hiring skilled employees initially reduces the need for extensive training, saving expenses.	Attracting and retaining talent reduces the costs associated with frequent recruitment, training, and the loss of productivity from employee turnover.
N	251	251	251	251	251
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum 1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum 5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.382	.665	.494	.523
	Positive	.135	.076	.088	.159
	Negative	-.382	-.665	-.494	-.523
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	6.059	10.541	7.827	8.284	9.215
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from $6.059 < 10.541$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that **Job analysis had significant positive relationship with employee output of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State.**

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from $6.059 < 10.541$ against the critical Z-value of 0.000 (2-tailed test at 95 percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that **Job analysis had significant positive relationship with employee output of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State.**

4.2.2 Hypotheses Two: Skill matching has significant relationship with employee retention of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	Training helps employees acquire new skills and update their knowledge, making them more competent in their roles	A trained workforce is better equipped to handle customer inquiries and provide excellent service, potentially leading to increased customer retention and satisfaction.	Increased revenue and reduced costs can lead to higher profits, allowing the bank to reinvest in further training and development.	A well-trained workforce is generally more productive, leading to greater output and reduced need for overtime or hiring additional staff.	Proper training can minimize errors, rework, and waste, contributing to efficiency and cost reduction.
N		251	251	251	251
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute Positive	.467	.698	.662	.583
	Negative	-.467	-.698	-.662	-.583
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		7.401	11.062	10.494	9.231
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from $7.590 < 11.062$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that **Skill matching had significant positive relationship with employee retention of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State.**

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from $7.590 < 11.062$ against the critical Z- value of 0.000 (2-tailed test at 95 percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that **Skill matching had significant positive relationship with employee retention of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State.**

4.3 Discussion of Findings

From the result of hypotheses one, the calculated Z- value ranges from $6.059 < 10.541$ against the critical Z- value of 0.000 which implies that Job analysis had significant positive relationship with employee output of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State. In the support of the result in the literature review,

From the result of hypotheses two, the calculated Z- value ranges from $7.590 < 11.062$ against the critical Z- value of 0.000 which implies that Skill matching had significant positive relationship with employee retention of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State. In the support of the result in the literature review,

5.0 Summary of Findings

- i. Job analysis had significant positive relationship with employee output of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State, $Z(10.541, P. < .05)$.
- ii. Skill matching had significant positive relationship with employee retention of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State, $Z(11.062, P. < .05)$.

5.1 Conclusion

The study concluded that Job analysis and Skill matching had significant positive relationship with employee output and employee retention of chemical manufacturing firms in Enugu State. Task allocation plays a critical role in enhancing employee productivity within chemical manufacturing firms. Properly assigning tasks based on workers' skills, experience, and specialization ensures that employees perform efficiently and with minimal errors. In the complex and high-risk environment of chemical production, clear task delineation reduces confusion, promotes accountability, and increases operational safety and efficiency. When task allocation is optimized, employees experience better job satisfaction, as they are assigned roles that match their competencies. Overall, strategic task allocation tailored to individual strengths and aligned with organizational goals significantly improves employee productivity and the overall performance of chemical manufacturing firms.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were proffered:

- i. To enhance employee output in chemical manufacturing firms, it is crucial to implement a structured and continuous job analysis process. Job analysis helps to clearly define roles, align responsibilities with organizational goals, and ensure that employees possess the necessary competencies for their positions.
- ii. Companies should institutionalize competency mapping report sharply to lower mishire rates and a measurable drop in voluntary turnover because new hires know exactly what success looks like and can see how to progress.

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